

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D5.8 Data Management Plan final version

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Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	6
2	Introduction.....	7
2.1	Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs.....	7
2.2	Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	8
2.3	Linkage to other project outputs.....	8
3	Data Management Approach	10
3.1	Overview.....	10
3.2	Ethics and GDPR compliance	11
3.3	Dissemination and communication of the research data	12
3.4	IP protection and exploitation of the research data and result	12
3.5	Processing of Personal Data Approach.....	13
3.6	Open Access to Research data proposed approach	14
3.7	Data Collection, Archiving & Preservation	14
3.8	FAIR Data Management.....	15
3.8.1	Making data findable	15
3.8.2	Making data accessible.....	17
3.8.3	Data interoperability	18
3.8.4	Data Reusability of Existing and Non-Existing Data.....	18
3.8.5	Longevity of the 5G-ROUTES research datasets.....	18
4	Data Lifecycle and Related Procedures	20
4.1	Roles and Responsibilities Regarding the Data Management Plan.....	22
4.2	DMP Registry Live Document	22
4.3	Data Collected Information per WP (M14).....	24
4.3.1	Data Overview	50
5	Conclusions.....	51
6	References.....	52
	Annex 1: DPO Appointment Template	53
	Annex 2: DPO Per Partner	54
	Annex 3: Data Protection Policy	55

List of Figures

Figure 1: 5G-ROUTES Data Management Plan	10
Figure 2: DOIs for Research Data [17]	16
Figure 3: 5G-ROUTES Data Lifecycle	20
Figure 4: Snapshot of the DMP Registry File	24

List of Tables

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.....	7
Table 2: Contributions of D5.8 from and to other project deliverables.....	8
Table 3: Daily Data Usage and Processes	11
Table 4: Data Management Report Template.....	21
Table 5: DMP Registry Template	23
Table 6: WP1 Data Management Plan.....	25
Table 7: WP2 Data Management Plan.....	28
Table 8: WP3 Data Management Plan.....	32
Table 9: WP4 Data Management Plan.....	36
Table 10: WP5 Data Management Plan.....	41
Table 11: WP6 Data Management Plan.....	45
Table 12: WP7 Data Management Plan.....	48

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AAM	Accepted Author Manuscript
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CC	Creative Commons
CERN	The European Organization for Nuclear Research (Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire)
CSL	Citation Style Language
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPIA	Data Privacy Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Directive
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
ISAN	International Standard Audio-Visual Number
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
ISRC	International Standard Recording Code
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
ISTC	International Standard Text Code
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ORD Pilot	Open Research Data Pilot
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
SWORD	Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the final version of the 5G-ROUTES Data Management Plan (DMP), summarising the work carried out under Task T5.3 – Innovation, Data Management, and IPR Activities (WP5). The DMP provides a comprehensive framework for managing, protecting, and sharing research data generated during the project, with a focus on compliance, security, and reusability. Key highlights include:

- **Guiding Principles:** Foundational data management principles applied throughout the project.
- **Legal Framework:** Compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- **Data Summary:** An overview of data collected and processed, including anonymized personal data where applicable.
- **FAIR Data Management:** Ensuring data is stored and processed according to the H2020 principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data.
- **Resource Allocation:** An outline of the costs associated with ensuring the data adheres to FAIR principles.
- **Data Security:** Robust measures to secure data and enable public sharing while mitigating risks.
- **Data Protection Officers:** Appointment of a Data Protection Officer (DPO) for each project partner to oversee compliance.

These procedures have established and implemented the FAIR data management framework in accordance with EC guidelines, aiming to ensure open accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data. As outlined in the EU Guidelines for Data Management Plans (DMPs), the DMP oversees all data generated and collected throughout the project, specifying the standards to be applied, the methods for preserving research data, and the portions of datasets to be shared for verification or reuse. The 5G-ROUTES DMP provides a foundation for identifying, curating, publishing, and sharing reusable research data assets.

The DMP ensures the protection of individuals' personal data collected and/or analysed as part of the project's key activities, in full compliance with applicable privacy and data protection laws and regulations. This is achieved through the establishment of mechanisms in collaboration with participating partners and the implementation of security measures and policies designed to safeguard the project against risks of personal data breaches. 5G-ROUTES actively participates in the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD Pilot) [1], an H2020 EU initiative aimed at improving access to and reuse of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects.

The project develops research methodologies to ensure that the data created or collected is suitable for open access following project completion. To comply with the Horizon 2020 Open Access Mandate, 5G-ROUTES utilized the open research data repositories Zenodo and Open Research Europe. This mandate primarily applies to the underlying research data of publications, but beneficiaries may also choose to make additional datasets openly available. All deliverables, publications, and anonymized portions of the underlying datasets generated by 5G-ROUTES will be uploaded to the European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) Community in Zenodo and Open Research Europe. These uploads will occur upon approval of deliverables by the European Commission, publication or acceptance of scientific outputs, or, at the latest, at the end of the project.

This final DMP includes updated instructions on accessing open data and reflects comprehensive data management processes implemented during the project. Data management and monitoring were conducted using an Excel file, updated quarterly, and stored in the SharePoint repository. This process ensured accurate and transparent documentation of data generation activities, supporting the project's goals of innovation, compliance, and sustainability.

2 Introduction

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this chapter is to map 5G-ROUTES' Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D5.8 Data Management Plan final version</i>	<i>Data Management Plan final version</i>	<i>Chapters 3-5 Annexes 1-3</i>	<i>As below</i>
TASKS			
<i>Task T5.3 – Innovation, data management and IPR activities</i>	<i>Data Management Plan (DMP) [TTU]: Development of the DMP, which will contain information related to the types of data the project will generate and collect, the standards that will be used to represent the data during the project and how partners might exploit the data resulting from the project. The DMP will set robust management procedures that will protect personal data collected as a result of project activities, as well as client owned data, from unauthorized use or sharing, also supporting GDPR compliance. In addition, the DMP will include a data protection impact assessment of 5G-ROUTES's requirements and field trials that will be used to ensure the project takes a data protection-by-design approach. The DMP will be produced at M06 and finalized in M33. The project's Data Protection Officer (DPO) will be available to assist - if needed - in decision-making as 5GROUTES is developed to identify potential risks, mitigation solutions and support compliance. All partners have appointed their own internal DPO</i>	<i>Chapters 3-5 Annexes 1-3</i>	<i>Chapter 2: Introduction of the deliverable and mapping with project outputs</i> <i>Chapter 3: Data Management Overview including Ethics and GDPR Compliance, procedures, open access and handling of personal data approach, FAIR Data Management compliance.</i> <i>Chapter 4: Data Lifecycle and Related Procedures. Initial DMP overview on collected data per WP/partner</i> <i>Chapter 5: Conclusion</i>

	<i>who will closely collaborate with the project's DPO.</i>		
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2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

In this chapter a description of the Deliverable's Structure is provided, outlining the respective Chapters and their content. A summary of the report structure and chapters of this report is presented below:

- Chapter 1: Executive summary.
- Chapter 2: Introduction of the deliverable and mapping with other project outputs (i.e. deliverables).
- Chapter 3: Data management approach following in the project, including Ethics and GDPR Compliance, procedures, open access, handling of personal data and comply with FAIR Data Management.
- Chapter 4: Data Lifecycle and related procedures. Also includes roles and responsibilities and an initial DMP overview on data collected per WP/partner.
- Chapter 5: Conclusion.

The report also includes annexes such as:

- Annex 1: Template used for appointment of DPO per partner
- Annex 2: List with DPO per partner
- Annex 3: Data Protection Policy

2.3 Linkage to other project outputs

Table 2: Contributions of D5.8 from and to other project deliverables

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	Deliverable Chapter(s)	Contribution and Value of linkage
INPUTS from other deliverables utilised in this report		
D7.7 Legal Framework-Ethics-Gender-Balance v1.0	Annexes V, VI, VII, VIII and IX	<p>The following are the templates for the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets obligatory to be used when conducting trials involving participants from outside the consortium:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed consent form example template • Anonymous Informed Consent Template • Non-Anonymous Informed Consent Template <p>The templates were initially established and included in 5G-ROUTES D7.7¹ and are part of the Ethics Protocol. In addition to the above templates, the following template is also included in D8.1 H – Requirement No.1 (Dissemination Level: CO):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-Disclosure Agreement for External Advisory Board Members <p>These templates are also referred in this document, in Section 3.2, to ensure synchronization between the Data Management Plan and Ethics and confirm that data collection complies with ethical requirements.</p>
D8.1 H – Requirement No.1	Section 5: Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets	
OUTPUTS from this report utilised by other deliverables		
D8.2 POPD - Requirement No. 2	Section 3: Data Management Overview	D8.2 (Dissemination Level: CO) has the below listed references to D5.7:

¹ 5G-ROUTES D7.7: https://www.5g-routes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/5G-ROUTES-D-7.7-LEGAL-FRAMEWORK-ETHICS-GENDER-BALANCE_2020-11-30_v1.0.pdf

	<p>Section 5.1: Roles and Responsibilities Regarding the Data Management Plan</p> <p>Annex 1: DPO Appointment Template</p> <p>Section 6: 5G-ROUTES Data Overview per WP</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Appointment of Data Protection Officers (DPOs)• Data management approach• Data Information Table for collecting information from partners <p>The expected benefit of utilizing the above information into the D8.2 is to connect the Data Management Plan during the set out of the 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with.</p>
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3 Data Management Approach

3.1 Overview

This chapter provides an overview of the guiding principles that were applied to manage research data throughout the 5G-ROUTES project and ensure its sustainability beyond the project's duration. It defines the data collection concepts, data purposes, and provides a detailed description of the procedures implemented for data collection, protection, and publication, ensuring the successful execution of this task.

Data management was a central theme in the project's monthly meetings, enabling continuous monitoring and updates to reflect any changes in partners' plans for data use. These discussions ensured that EBOS, supported by ILS, remained informed of evolving requirements and facilitated the ongoing alignment of data management activities with project objectives.

Figure 1: 5G-ROUTES Data Management Plan

Figure 1 provides an overview of the data management approach implemented in the 5G-ROUTES project. Data collected, generated, and shared across various Work Packages (WPs) were systematically organized into distinct categories, including Contractual, Deliverables, Financials, Management, and WP-specific files. The data encompassed a diverse range of types, such as trial raw data (datasets), narrative texts, numerical data, images, audio files, video files, internal and external reports, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), statistics, figures, questionnaires, checklists, user input, and feedback.

To ensure secure and efficient management, all data were aggregated and stored in the project's SharePoint repository, hosted by ILS. This centralized repository played a critical role in supporting project activities by providing a reliable foundation for analyses, enabling the preparation of deliverables, facilitating scientific publications, and driving exploitation activities. This robust data management system ensured compliance with project requirements and promoted collaboration among partners. (Section 3.4).

Throughout the project, collected data was consistently evaluated for:

- **Compliance** with Ethics and GDPR requirements, as outlined in D7.7 Legal Framework-Ethics-Gender-Balance v1.0.
- **Eligibility** for dissemination and publication.
- **Suitability** for intellectual property (IP) protection and potential exploitation.

3.2 Ethics and GDPR compliance

The 5G-ROUTES project addresses privacy and data protection concerns by collecting data from project participants within EU countries. To ensure compliance, the following informed consent/assent form templates and information sheets were mandatory for trials involving participants outside the consortium:

- Informed consent form example template
- Anonymous Informed Consent Template
- Non-Anonymous Informed Consent Template

The above-mentioned templates were established and included in D7.7 and are part of the Ethics Protocol. In addition to the above templates, the following template is also included in D8.1 H – Requirement No.1:

- Non-Disclosure Agreement for External Advisory Board Members

Chapter 6 - 5G-ROUTES Data Management Overview per WP, provides the final list of all data/datasets that were generated in the 5G-ROUTES project and their accessibility. This list was updated as the project progressed.

The Global Data Protection Policy (the "Policy") was prepared by EBOS for the 5G-ROUTES project (Contract Number 951867) and applies to all participating partners. The Policy ensures compliance with:

- The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): EU 2016/679, effective since May 25, 2018.
- Other applicable national and EU regulations and guidelines concerning personal data processing.
- Best practices and regulatory standards for research projects under the EU H2020 Research Programme.

The subsequent chapters detail the procedures implemented in 5G-ROUTES to ensure data protection compliance. GDPR applies to all personal data collected during project activities, with more information about the Policy available in [Annex 3](#).

To meet GDPR requirements, the 5G-ROUTES consortium established several process-related policies to standardize data usage, storage, and management during daily project operations. These policies, agreed upon by all partners, are outlined in the accompanying table, detailing the procedures followed by the consortium.

Table 3: Daily Data Usage and Processes

Process	Description
Contacts Information	The 5G-ROUTES list of contacts is a single .XLS file containing details of consortium partners, including Name, Surname, Email Address, Role in the Project, and Emailing Lists. This file is securely stored in the SharePoint repository with restricted access (login required). Its primary purpose is to streamline communication among partners. This data will be retained for five years.
Meeting Material	Includes documents such as agendas, presentations, minutes, and signature lists prepared for project meetings. These documents are securely stored in SharePoint under the "Meetings" section with access restricted to consortium partners. Retention is for five years to ensure compliance and traceability.
Workshops and Training Material	Consists of materials related to workshops, including agendas, participant lists, presentations, video recordings, and photos. This material is fully anonymized to exclude any personal information. Stored securely in SharePoint under the "Workshops" section, with restricted access. Retention period: five years.
Dissemination Material	Dissemination activities, such as newsletters, social media posts, and other promotional materials, are managed by the Project Coordinator. Personal data is processed to: (1) Collect and store relevant data, (2) Monitor communications, (3) Provide instructions for dissemination activities, and (4) Inform partners of policy updates.
Reporting material	Includes documents prepared for internal and external (EC) reporting on project progress, technical summaries, and financial data, which may include personal information. These documents are stored securely in SharePoint and are used by partners to claim budgets and report efforts. Retention period: five years.
Deliverables, Internal	During the 5G-ROUTES project lifetime, all project-related documents, including deliverables and internal reports, are stored in SharePoint under the "Deliverables" section. Access is

Process	Description
Documents, and other Reports	restricted to consortium partners (login required). Public deliverables are also uploaded to the project website. Retention period: five years.
Usage of Cookies	Any 5G-ROUTES web application employing cookies includes a pop-up notification to inform users and prompt consent for personal information storage.
Project related research data	Data used internally for research purposes, such as trial and use case data, is fully anonymized by the data owner (controller). No personal information is included, ensuring compliance with GDPR and project guidelines.
Personal data related to external stakeholders	Personal data from external stakeholders is partially derived from the 5G-ROUTES internal contact lists and direct communications. This information is managed in a GDPR-compliant database and system for e-communication purposes.

3.3 Dissemination and communication of the research data

Non-confidential data was utilized to create public deliverables, publications, promotional materials, and other outputs, which will be disseminated to specific stakeholder groups or the broader public. All publications will adhere to the project's Data Management Plan (DMP) and will be shared via open research data repositories such as Zenodo [2] and Open Research Europe [3].

Zenodo, a versatile open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program, enables researchers to deposit various digital artifacts, including research papers, datasets, software, and reports. Each submission is assigned a persistent Digital Object Identifier (DOI), ensuring the content is easily citable. Similarly, Open Research Europe is an open-access platform that allows researchers to publish their work, supporting transparency, reproducibility, and impact. Its open publishing model ensures rapid publication within days of submission, followed by an open peer review process. Both repositories include citations for all supporting data and materials, facilitating reanalysis, replication, and reuse.

Both green and gold open access publications and their underlying data are required to be deposited in these repositories. While the project agreement specifies green open access, gold access has also been considered due to its growing adoption within academic and research institutions. Authors must deposit a machine-readable electronic copy (e.g., the accepted author manuscript or final PDF) in a repository promptly, and no later than publication. For green open access, authors are required to include a link to the final version, with the accepted author manuscript (AAM)—the final peer-reviewed manuscript incorporating reviewer comments but without publisher formatting—being the preferred version for deposit.

Once reviewed and approved by the European Commission (EC), all public deliverables will be openly shared via the 5G-ROUTES website and open research data repositories. Publications will strictly follow the guidelines outlined in the project's DMP and Intellectual Property (IP) Management Strategy.

3.4 IP protection and exploitation of the research data and result

During the regular monthly meetings, project partners discussed the potential of the project's results that could lead to commercial exploitation and determined appropriate measures to protect the associated data. These discussions were monitored by the Innovation Manager (ILS), who ensured that any such cases were addressed by implementing steps to safeguard these results for potential exploitation. A key focus of Innovation Management in 5G-ROUTES has been the creation of an Innovation Registry that was used as a tool for capturing, consolidating, and monitoring innovation produced in the project and documenting information about the benefits to the innovators and to the project and envisioned evolution of the innovation during and after the end of the project. Additional information can be found in Deliverable D5.6 Innovation management plan and IP protection report final version.

As illustrated in Figure 1, data underlying commercially exploitable results were not openly shared. Instead, this data was securely archived in the project's internal storage, and the corresponding deliverable was shared

exclusively with the European Commission during the regular project reviews. This approach ensured the protection of sensitive information while fulfilling the project's reporting obligations.

3.5 Processing of Personal Data Approach

This section provides a comprehensive review of how personal data was utilized within the 5G-ROUTES project, categorized by Work Package (WP) and Partner. All personal data handling adhered strictly to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679, ensuring compliance with European privacy standards. The 5G-ROUTES consortium demonstrated a strong commitment to ethical data handling practices, respecting national regulations and laws, and continually refining its approach to data processing, ethical principles, and innovation conduct.

Given their extensive experience and training in research and innovation methodologies, 5G-ROUTES partners were well-versed in the ethical requirements associated with research involving human participants. The consortium implemented the following principles to ensure responsible handling of personal data:

1. **Informed Consent:**
 - All test subjects, and their legal guardians when applicable, were fully informed about monitoring and data acquisition processes.
 - Participation was strictly voluntary, and all subjects received detailed oral and written information prior to engagement.
2. **Transparency in Stakeholder Engagement:**
 - Testing, trials, workshops, and other activities were conducted with participants who were fully informed of their roles in the project, the data being collected, and how it would be processed, stored, anonymized, and peer-reviewed before use (e.g., in publications or system innovations).
 - Covert data collection (without participants' knowledge or consent) was strictly prohibited.
3. **Explicit Consent for Data Collection:**
 - No personal data was collected without explicit informed consent from participants and their legal guardians (if applicable).
 - Participants were clearly informed about the procedures and objectives of the research and provided explicit agreement before any data was collected.
4. **Participant Information and Risks:**
 - Participants were made aware of the beneficiaries of their participation, as well as the risks or burdens associated with their involvement.
 - Information on the potential commercial exploitation of the project's innovations was transparently communicated.
5. **Voluntary Participation and Withdrawal Rights:**
 - Participation was entirely voluntary, with participants encouraged to ask questions and receive clear answers before making decisions.
 - Participants retained the right to withdraw and terminate their participation at any time and were reminded of this right before participation.
6. **Data Storage and Anonymization:**
 - Personal and sensitive data were not centrally stored. Where applicable, data were scrambled or abstracted to ensure no impact on the project's outcomes.
 - Anonymization techniques ensured that participants' identities remained protected.
7. **Restricted Data Usage:**
 - Data collected during the project was strictly used for the purposes of the 5G-ROUTES project and was not sold or repurposed for other activities.
8. **Data Minimization Policy:**
 - A data minimization policy was enforced across all project activities, ensuring only the data strictly necessary for completing the study was collected.
 - This policy was supervised by the Project Coordinator and Data Protection Officers (DPOs) appointed by each partner.

9. Protection Against Privacy Breaches:

- Specific measures were implemented to protect participants from breaches of privacy or confidentiality and any form of discrimination.
- Personal identifiers, such as participant names, were not disclosed publicly, and participation details were kept confidential.
- Incidental findings were treated with strict confidentiality and erased upon request from the enrolled subject.

3.6 Open Access to Research data proposed approach

Since 2017, all thematic areas under the H2020 Programme have been included in the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD Pilot), a flexible initiative promoting open access to research data and scientific publications. The ORD Pilot aims to balance the benefits of open data with the need to protect scientific information, support commercialization and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), address privacy concerns, ensure security, and manage data preservation effectively.

The H2020 strategy for fostering a smart, sustainable, and inclusive economy emphasizes the pivotal role of knowledge and innovation in driving growth. The ORD Pilot was introduced to improve the quality of research by enabling free access to scientific publications and data, encouraging collaboration, preventing duplication of effort, accelerating market entry, and showcasing the value of public investment in research. These benefits extend to researchers, citizens, and society as a whole.

From a broader perspective, open access (OA) provides free online access to scientific information, promoting data reusability. Within research and development (R&D), OA typically addresses two main data categories: scientific publications and research data from experiments. Research data includes facts or figures collected for examination and analysis, such as statistics, experimental results, field observations, survey outcomes, interview recordings, and images, with a focus on data available in digital form.

The ORD Pilot, managed by the European Commission, applies to datasets underlying scientific publications and peer-reviewed papers from H2020 projects. Following principles outlined in the Budapest Declaration (2002) and Berlin Declaration (2003), open access extends beyond downloading, saving, and printing documents. It includes rights to copy, distribute, search, link, and mine data. The Data Management Plan (DMP) identifies which data will be shared and any applicable restrictions.

The two main routes to open access, as also presented in Figure 1 above, are the following:

- **Self-archiving / 'green' open access** – the author, or a representative, archives (deposits) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication. Some publishers request that open access be granted only after an embargo period has elapsed.
- **Open access publishing / 'gold' open access** - To go through with this option, the author will need to pay for immediate open access. This can either be by publishing in specific open access journals or in so called hybrid open access journals, where one pays for online open. In both cases the author gets immediate access to the high-quality PDF of the manuscript. The publication is usually covered by the Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) license, meaning that the publisher only gets a license to publish the publication but the actual copyright stays with author(s) [6][7][8].

As of the time of writing this deliverable, there are currently 44 5G-ROUTES-related items, including publications and deliverables, available in Zenodo.

3.7 Data Collection, Archiving & Preservation

All data and information collected during project activities were analysed, refined, organized, and stored in a secure data repository accessible to all project partners. To effectively track the collected data, WP Leader was responsible for defining and describing datasets specific to their respective WPs. This was achieved using an Excel file titled “DMP Registry” (refer to Table 2), stored on the project’s SharePoint repository with restricted access limited to consortium partners. Details and results of this process are presented in Section 4.3.

Throughout the project, all datasets were stored in the SharePoint repository, which serves as the project's centralized file storage and collaboration platform. If necessary, data stored on SharePoint can remain accessible for up to five years following the project's conclusion to facilitate final closing activities, after which it will be permanently deleted. The internal structure of the WP folders was determined by each WP Leader. Data-generating partners were responsible for uploading their datasets to SharePoint, while WP Leaders conducted periodic reviews of the folders to ensure datasets were archived appropriately and in compliance with DMP procedures.

At the end of the project, all final datasets, public deliverables, and publications will be transferred to Zenodo and Open Research Europe repositories, ensuring the sustainable archiving of research outputs. Items deposited in these repositories are preserved for the duration of their respective lifetimes. For Zenodo, this corresponds to the lifetime of its host laboratory, CERN, which has an experimental Programme defined for at least the next 20 years, as stated in Zenodo's General Policies [9].

3.8 FAIR Data Management

FAIR data management aligns with the European Commission's guidelines to ensure that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. In the 5G-ROUTES project, FAIR data principles were applied to establish consistent naming conventions, facilitate contributions to open data research, enhance data identification and searchability, and ensure the provision of metadata to support data reusability. The project aimed to maximize access to and reuse of the research data it generated. However, certain datasets, or parts thereof, were not shared to safeguard commercially exploitable results and protect the privacy of voluntary participants involved in workshops.

3.8.1 Making data findable

5G-ROUTES will use the Zenodo and Open Research Europe repositories as the main tools to make projects' research data findable in accordance with the H2020 Open Access Mandate. A H2020 5G-ROUTES community will be established on both Zenodo and Open Research Europe websites, and the project will upload all our public datasets and deliverables as well as scientific publications to this community. In addition, we will link all projects' uploads to the European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) community for maximum findability. Some more information about making data available over Zenodo is followed.

All uploads will be enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including Grant Number and Project Acronym. Zenodo provides version control and assigns DOIs to all uploaded elements. The consortium will make use of metadata to describe the data collection and to facilitate the finding and re-use of data. Metadata will have a twofold nature: descriptive, therefore giving information on the data discovery and identification (titles, author, keywords) and administrative outlining when and how data was created, file type and other technical information, and who can access it. Metadata associated with each published data set in Zenodo will by default be as follows:

- Digital Object Identifiers
- Version numbers
- Bibliographic information
- Keywords
- Abstract/description
- Associated project and community
- Associated publications and reports
- Grant information
- Access and licensing info
- Language

Each partner will be responsible for uploading public datasets that they have generated and assign specific keywords relevant to these datasets. Dataset specific keywords must be descriptive to the content of the dataset. In addition, a set of general keywords that should apply to all public datasets, scientific publications, and public

deliverables. In the framework of 5G-ROUTES quality plan and control, a series of documents/reports templates have been created to ensure a consistent approach for all 5G-ROUTES data and their versions.

Zenodo supports DOI versioning [10] (see Figure 2), which allows users to update datasets after they have been made public and researchers to easily cite either specific versions of a record or to cite, via a top-level DOI, all the versions of a record. DOI stands for "Digital Object Identifier", meaning a "digital identifier of an object". As outlined in the DOI handbook [11]:

- The DOI syntax is be made up of a DOI prefix and a DOI suffix separated by a forward slash. The DOI prefix is composed of a directory indicator followed by a registrant code.
 - The directory indicator is always "10".
 - The registrant code is a unique string assigned to a registrant (i.e. 5072).
 - The directory indicator and the registrant code are separated by a dot ".".
- The DOI suffix consists of a character string of any length chosen by the registrant. Each suffix shall be unique to the prefix element that precedes it. The unique suffix can be a sequential number, or it might incorporate an identifier generated from or based on another system used by the registrant (i.e. ISAN [12], ISBN [13], ISRC [14], ISSN [15], ISTC [16], etc.)

Zenodo registers one DOI per version of the dataset, and in addition one Concept DOI is registered. The Concept DOI represents all versions of a record, and semantically link all the per-version DOIs.

As an example, DOI versioning of a dataset that is released in several versions can look like this:

- v1.0: 10.5072/zenodo.123
- v2.0: 10.5072/zenodo.321
- Concept (all versions): 10.5072/zenodo.122

The first two DOIs for versions v1.0 and v.2.0 represent the specific versions of the dataset, while the Concept (the last DOI) represents all the versions of the dataset package, i.e. the concept of the dataset and the ensemble of versions. They are referred to as Version DOIs and Concept DOIs, but in fact they are both normal DOIs.

This does not, however, mean that a new DOI will be assigned each time the metadata of the dataset is edited (i.e. change the title of a file or dataset). A new DOI version will only be created if one updates the actual files that have been uploaded.

Figure 2: DOIs for Research Data [17]

The H2020 Open Access Mandate aims to make research data generated by H2020 projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, but also accept protection of personal or sensitive data due to privacy concerns and/or commercial or security reasons. All public datasets, scientific publications and deliverables will be

uploaded to Zenodo and made openly available, free of charge. Publications and underlying data sets will be linked through use of persistent identifiers (DOI versioning). Datasets and publications which are "confidential" will not be shared due to privacy concerns or potential for commercial exploitation. If such cases arise during the project, this will be informed in the final version of the DMP.

Metadata including licenses for individual data records as well as record collections will be harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. The data will be available through Zenodo and hence accessible using any web browsing application.

3.8.2 Making data accessible

This DMP supports the 5G-ROUTES initiative to contribute data to the Open Research Data Pilot. To qualify for sharing, datasets are evaluated to ensure that:

- They are non-confidential and do not include personal or commercially sensitive information.
- Relevant permissions have been obtained from stakeholders and/or data subjects, and sharing does not compromise exploitation opportunities or Intellectual Property (IP) protection, in line with the processes outlined in Innovation, IPR, and Data Management.

Datasets are reviewed collaboratively by the 5G-ROUTES Project Coordinator, Innovation Manager, WP Leaders, and the Data Protection Officer (DPO) assigned by each partner (Annex 2). Only endorsed datasets will be considered for inclusion in the Open Research Data Pilot. Following approval, the originating consortium partner(s) and the responsible parties will agree on a licensing framework (e.g., Creative Commons or Public Domain). Once approved in principle, 5G-ROUTES will ensure datasets are accessible through suitable open access repositories, in accordance with the guidelines specified in the Grant Agreement.

Final approval for open data publication must be communicated to the Project Coordinator by the data owners via email. This approval must explicitly include consent for the distribution of the data beyond the 5G-ROUTES consortium. The email should include the following details:

- **Data Processor**
- **Description of the Data** (what the data includes)
- **Data Filenames and Version**
- **Consent to Publish Data** outside the 5G-ROUTES consortium.

This process ensures that data sharing aligns with ethical, legal, and strategic considerations while contributing to the goals of open research.

The following repository systems is used and will be used in 5G-ROUTES Project:

- **SharePoint Repository:** Already mentioned in Section 3.7. It will be used as the Project main file repository and documentation/data exchange among consortium partners. It also serves as centralized access to the relevant information and documents of importance to monitor the progresses in the project and to promote communication between partners, revisions of documents and their repository. SharePoint will be the main server where all project data will be shared and exchanged between the different beneficiaries. SharePoint is also used for editing the DMP Registry tables by the WP Leaders / Consortium Partners online. Access is restricted to the consortium members. SharePoint is considered as GDPR Compliant².
- **Zenodo & Open Research Europe:** All scientific publications, including public deliverables and public parts of underlying datasets will be uploaded to the H2020 5G-ROUTES Community in addition to the European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) Community in Zenodo. Zenodo is a "catch-all" open research data repository which gathers research data across all disciplinary fields. Open Research Europe enables researchers to publish any research they wish to share, supporting reproducibility, transparency, and impact. Uses an open research publishing model: publication within days of submission, followed by

² GDPR Compliancy with OneDrive and SharePoint: <https://techcommunity.microsoft.com/blog/onedriveblog/gdpr-compliancy-with-onedrive-and-sharepoint/191126>

open invited peer review. Includes citations to all supporting data and materials, enabling reanalysis, replication, and reuse.

3.8.3 Data interoperability

Data interoperability within the 5G-ROUTES project was primarily designed for internal purposes, encompassing data reuse, interchange, and general utilization across the consortium. For interoperability beyond the consortium, the project adhered to IPR rules to ensure no 5G-ROUTES foreground information was inadvertently disclosed. Detailed guidelines on external data sharing and IP-related considerations are provided in Section 4 of this report.

To enhance data interoperability, the consortium made every effort to use standard file formats such as .XML, .XLS(X), and other commonly recognized formats. Additionally, 5G-ROUTES explored the adoption of internationally recognized standards for both the data and software produced during the project.

The project prioritized the standardized collection and documentation of data to ensure datasets were understandable, reusable, and interoperable among diverse stakeholders. Standard technical terminology was employed to facilitate interdisciplinary interoperability. The vocabularies used for data and metadata interoperability included standard vocabularies such as OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) and SWORD (Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit).

Zenodo uses JSON schema as the internal representation of metadata and offers export to other formats such as DublinCore (Dublin Core Metadata Element Set) [18], MARCXML (MARC 21 XML Schema) [19], BibTeX [20], Citation Style Language (CSL) [21], DataCite Metadata Schema [22] and export to Mendeley [23]. The data record metadata will utilize the vocabularies applied by Zenodo. For certain terms, these refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE). Reference to any external metadata is done with a resolvable URL.

3.8.4 Data Reusability of Existing and Non-Existing Data

Existing data within the scope of the 5G-ROUTES project refers to data that pre-dates and was not generated by the project's activities. The consortium ensures that such data is correctly and securely stored on appropriate servers or storage systems, enabling controlled access to authorized users while maintaining robust security measures.

The reuse of data is a key principle of FAIR data management, allowing datasets to serve purposes beyond their original intent. At this stage, the licensing models for the various data products produced within 5G-ROUTES are yet to be finalized. Licensing decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis in close collaboration with the Coordinator, Innovation Manager, and relevant partners.

The 5G-ROUTES project is committed to enabling third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce, and disseminate all public datasets free of charge. This will be governed by the application of Creative Commons (CC) Attribution Licenses, which provide flexible copyright permissions for creative works. By default, the CC-BY-SA license will be applied to public 5G-ROUTES datasets. This license allows others to remix, adapt, and build upon the data for commercial purposes, provided the original authors are credited and any derivative works are licensed under identical terms. This aligns with the principles of "copyleft" and open-source software licensing. Where applicable, less restrictive licenses such as CC-BY or more restrictive ones like CC-BY-NC (which prohibits commercial usage) may be considered, based on the nature of the data and its intended use. Through these measures, the project ensures compliance with FAIR principles while maximizing the impact and accessibility of its research outputs.

3.8.5 Longevity of the 5G-ROUTES research datasets

For data published in scientific journals, the underlying datasets were made available no later than the date of the journal's publication, with links provided to the associated publication. Data related to public deliverables were shared upon their approval and acceptance by the European Commission (EC). Other public datasets not directly tied to a scientific publication or deliverable were assessed by the consortium and published no later than the final month of the project.

Open data can be reused under the terms of Creative Commons licenses. Confidential data, by default, is not reusable due to privacy concerns. Publicly shared data will remain accessible and reusable via Zenodo for at least 20 years, as guaranteed by Zenodo's host organization, CERN. In the event that Zenodo ceases operations, all content, including metadata, will be migrated to a suitable alternative repository to ensure continued accessibility.

Confidential data will be deleted at the conclusion of the project. However, in cases where permission was granted by the data owner, certain non-anonymized data may be retained for up to five years following the project's contractual end date. This extended period ensures availability for completing scientific publications initiated toward the end of the project.

An exception applies to materials such as images and videos used for communication purposes. These materials will be retained for up to five years after the project ends to meet EC contractual obligations, supporting continued dissemination and exploitation activities.

4 Data Lifecycle and Related Procedures

This chapter explains the whole data life cycle that will be taking place in the 5G-ROUTES project. 5G-ROUTES considers the different stages at which data is created, managed, or utilised during the whole project lifecycle.

Figure 3: 5G-ROUTES Data Lifecycle

The previous Figure 3 indicates the 5G-ROUTES data lifecycle in a typical flow with several processes/stages as also listed and explained below.

- **Data Creation and Collection:** This stage includes the data creation and/or collection based on projects' activities and the various data provided by the trials, the project reports (i.e. deliverables) as well as other documents or spreadsheets. This includes the creation of the data (by the respective owner) and the collection in a structured and format manner, and layouts to enable their processing by the other project components or partners.
- **Data Processing and Analysis:** This stage is related to the actual data processing by the various data processors. Processors are the partners that will have access to the data based on project needs and expected outcomes. During this stage we need to ensure that the processors can perform data processing in a concise approach, including data verification, organization, transformation, integration, and extraction for the intended use, to fulfil the project needs. Data analysis includes all the actions and methodology performed on the actual data that describes existing facts, identify outlines, develop data clarifications, etc.
- **Data Publication and Utilisation:** This stage includes the publication of data, meaning the need to share data openly to the public. Moreover, utilization includes the steps towards data sharing, internally to projects' Consortium. Controlling mechanisms need to be in place to ensure that the data is shared with the appropriate protection of proprietary data as well as the data integrity itself. Finally, this stage is closely linked with the next stage (data storage and archiving) as far as metadata is related to ensure data searchability.
- **Data Storage, Archiving and Reuse:** The storage and archiving stage is critical as it is related to the data access, storage, sharing, archiving and re-usage. This should also involve actions to ensure accidental data loss or deletion, data corruption or even unauthorized access to the data. Data storage and archiving is also strongly linked to data reusability that is also part of the FAIR data treatment.

In each of the above-mentioned steps, specific metrics have been identified to be followed related to the data management along with controls (summarised into the data management report template - Table 4 below). This template was used at various project stages to control data management compliancy.

Table 4: Data Management Report Template

Performance Indicator	Verification Method	Target	Compliance
Data Creation and Collection			
Data format	Compliance with existing standards of data exchange	.XLS, .XML, .DOC, etc.	[Y/N]
Availability and Readability	Whole set of data available, non-corrupted, and collected	Fully accessibility	[Y/N]
Fit for Use	Data follow data compliancy for proper processing and review	Fully usable by intended beneficiary	[Y/N]
Consistency and Completeness	Data are consistent and complete for the intended purpose	Fully information included	[Y/N]
Relation	Data follow a precise relation to their purpose	Fully purpose precision	[Y/N]
Data Processing and Analysis			
Data logic	Data can be processed following a concise logic and approach	New and processed data fully follow precise data logic	[Y/N]
Organization and Utility	Data under processing to have suitable content organization	Fully organized data	[Y/N]
Validation	Ensuring that the processed data are correct and relevant	Fully validated and relevant data	[Y/N]
Aggregation	In case multiple data needs to be aggregated, ensure that this process is done in a concise approach	Fully aggregate-able data	[Y/N]
Transformation	Transformation of data to the proper format(s) for processing	Capability of data for transformation (if needed)	[Y/N]
Calibration	Calibration of data if required	Data properly calibrated	[Y/N]
Data Publication and Utilization			
Means-independent	Transferring of the data in a means-independent approach	Fully means independent transferability	[Y/N]
Security	Data stored in a secure location (i.e. database, server)	Accessing controls are provided along with detailed storage information	[Y/N]
Data Storage, Archiving and Reuse			
Up to date	Ensuring that the stored data are up to date and no later version exists	Fully updated	[Y/N]
Metadata	Existence of metadata in stored files	Relevant metadata have been included into the archive per dataset	[Y/N]
Security	Access control provided along with storing information (Project cloud server is considered as safe enough)	Access controls (Transport Layer Security protocol preferable) and detailed storage information	[Y/N]
Expiration	Properly set of date (or duration) after which the data will be deleted	Expiration date properly setup	[Y/N]

4.1 Roles and Responsibilities Regarding the Data Management Plan

WP5 and, Task 5.3 is responsible for the data management lifecycle monitoring for all datasets to be collected, processed, or generated by the project. To ensure compliance with data management decisions as they relate to the DMP, the following roles and responsibilities were applied in 5G-ROUTES.

- **5G-ROUTES DPO:** for the overall 5G-ROUTES project activities, the Project coordinator (ERICSSON) is considered as the project's DPO which will be available to assist - if needed - in decision-making as 5GROUTES is developed to identify potential risks, mitigation solutions and support compliance. In the case of personal data processing, Project coordinator will serve as the project's DPO assisted by the DPO point of contact of each of the consortium's members, to manage such data.
- **WP Leaders:** are considered responsible for adhering to the specifications mentioned above, and the monitoring and handling of the data generated by each participant in the WP they are leading.
- **Appointed Data Protection Officer (DPO) per partner:** Following and completing an official appointment template provided by the Project ([Annex 1](#)), each partner has assigned a dedicated DPO for the project ([Annex 2](#)). Each DPO, along with the personnel of each organisation (assigned and working on the project) are considered responsible for the management of the project's collected data within their organisation. They should also ensure that personnel working on the project have read the data management plan and apply/exercise all the principles as described in the 5G-ROUTES DMP (this document).
- **Data Processors:** partner(s) working with the data produced by the project. Data processors have the responsibility of complying with the specifics of the 5G-ROUTES Data Management plan, as well as to the related Ethics requirements and GPDR policies ([Chapter 3.2](#)).
- **Innovation Manager:** EBOS as the project's Innovation Manager acts as the main advisor on any data related issue during the project lifecycle. It is also the responsible partner for the setup of the Projects' Data Management Plan and procedures to be followed.

4.2 DMP Registry Live Document

This chapter outlines the data collection concepts and purposes as they relate to the 5G-ROUTES project's work breakdown structure. Following consultations with the 5G-ROUTES WP Leaders, the following key elements were defined and documented:

- Lead Partner
- Owner of the data
- Data Origin
- Data Type(s)
- Purpose of collecting
- Data Processing Activities
- Data Format
- Quantity (Approximated Data Size)
- Public / Confidential
- Storage Location
- Which partner will use the data / has access to it?

To maintain accurate records of the collected data, each WP Leader was responsible for defining and describing the datasets specific to their work package. This was accomplished by completing an Excel file titled "DMP Registry," securely stored on SharePoint with access restricted to consortium partners.

As shown in the Table 5 below, the DMP Registry provides both qualitative and quantitative descriptions of the project datasets, ensuring comprehensive documentation and traceability.

Table 5: DMP Registry Template

Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Name of the lead partner responsible for dataset generation, collection, processing.
Owner of the data	Who is the owner of the data
Data Origin	Description of the origin of the data (lab tests, computer simulation,
Data Type(s)	Type of data contained in the dataset e.g. narrative texts, numbers, images, audio files, video files, internal/external reports, KPIs, statistics, figures, questionnaires, check lists, user stories.
Purpose of collecting	The purpose of the data collection/generation?
Data Processing Activities	Actions performed on those data (share, edit, use for statistics, etc.)
Data Format	Data format could be: .doc/.docx, .xls/.xlsx, .pdf, .ppt/.pptx etc.
Quantity (Approximated Data Size)	Approximate size of dataset in Mb/Gb and number of files
Public / Confidential to the Consortium	Public data: made available to other researchers through the EC's repositories or through the project. Confidential to the consortium: data that cannot be exposed in public (including information included in confidential deliverables)
Personal Data (Yes/No)	Mark Yes or No if the collected data includes personal information
Storage Location	Where is data stored on the server i.e. name of the server + path.
Data Storage Duration	The duration the data will be stored (i.e. project duration or more, and why)
Which partner will use the data / has access to it?	Who has access to the data? And what type of access is it, i.e. viewing, editing, etc.

The DMP Registry file functioned as a "living document," meaning it was continuously accessible online and restricted exclusively to consortium partners. While SharePoint is considered GDPR-compliant, no personal data or raw data collected during the project were stored directly within the DMP Registry file. Instead, the file's purpose was to serve as an evolving record, regularly updated to document the types of data collected by each partner without hosting the actual data.

Within the DMP Registry file, a column titled "Data Storage Location" allowed partners to specify where their data was physically stored (e.g., SharePoint, databases, etc.). This ensured clear traceability of the data while

maintaining the privacy and security of sensitive information. A snapshot of the current DMP Registry file is provided in the Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Snapshot of the DMP Registry File

As previously mentioned, each WP Leader was responsible for defining and describing all datasets collected within their respective WP. To ensure proper tracking, the DMP Registry file was updated at predefined intervals every three months, following collaboration with the partners involved in their WP, throughout the project’s duration. Additionally, the DMP was required to be updated whenever significant changes occurred, including but not limited to:

- Collection of new data (e.g., during trial periods).
- Changes in consortium policies (e.g., new innovation opportunities).
- Changes in consortium composition or external factors (e.g., new members joining or existing members leaving).
- Periodic evaluation and assessment milestones of the project.

Data management and updates to the DMP Registry were continuously monitored by EBOS as part of the activities under WP5. To maintain a history of changes made to the DMP Registry, each updated version (every three months) was exported and securely stored in the project repository on SharePoint. This ensured that all modifications were traceable and well-documented throughout the project lifecycle.

4.3 Data Collected Information per WP

The tables below present detailed information on the datasets collected by consortium partners up to M53. Organized by WP and partners, these tables provide a comprehensive overview of the data generated throughout the project. Instances of "N/A" in the tables signify that the specific information was either not applicable or unavailable during the data collection process.

Table 6: WP1 Data Management Plan

Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
EEE	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ADS	ADS and use case owner	Use cases analysis	Satellite connectivity KPIs	project needs	N/A	mainly .doc	tbd	both	No	5G-Routes Project Repository	project duration	Consortium partners
ADSF	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
PV	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ATOS	N/A	UC4	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
BRA	BRA, ADSF, VTT	Use cases analysis	Use cases KPIs and requirements, Deliverable 1.1 and 1.7 contributions	Use case needs and objectives	N/A	.doc	N/A	Public	No	5G-Routes Project Repository	SharePoint project file repository	Consortium partners
CTTC	CTTC	CTTC 5G testbed	logs to validate deployments of use cases to be ready for execution to start checking KPI collection methods by UC owners	project needs	N/A	.txt	N/A	Confidential	No	CTTC	project duration	use case owners deploying with CAM Services platform
EBOS	UC Leaders	requirements for the tenant portal	N/A	project needs	N/A	.doc	N/A	both	No	5G-Routes Project Repository	project duration	Consortium partners
EVR	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ENIDE	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
CERTH	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ILS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

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VED	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
IQU	IQU	CTTC testbed, innovation of technological enablers	KPIs, Requirements	project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	IQU	N/A	Consortium partners
LMT	LMT	Gathered data about 5G network architecture & functionalities, public sources for elaboration of WP1 deliverables.	Different 5G network and UCs data, analysis, etc. public information required for elaboration of D1.3,D1.4, D1.10 and partners WP1 Deliverables.	project needs	N/A	mainly doc, xlsx, graphs, images	N/A	Both	No	5G-Routes Project Repository	Project duration	Consortium partners
SWA	City of Valga/ SWA	Data acquired from devices installed in specific locations to develop the trials	Traffic Light Data, Sensors Data	Base for C-ITS services	Elaboration of C-ITS messages	ETSI standards for C-ITS (in output), proprietary formats (in input)	Real time data per one intersection	Confidential	No	SWA Cloud	Raw data - 1 week, Aggregated KPIs - Project duration	Partners will only be able to access the services
TTU	TTU	UC3.2 + TTU 5G-IoT testbed and TTU 5G D2D SideLink testbed	Data from OBD dongles/sensors (monitor vehicles' condition).	Execution of UC3.2 and other project usecases	Developing machine learning algorithms for UC3.2	REST, JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) and MQTT.	Thousands of records	both		TTU	Project duration	UC leaders and participants

VTT	VTT	data collected from partners and public sources for use cases definition and test framework Measurement data for maritime solution network performance	data and KPIs regarding use cases; for maritime: data collected using Nemo and Qosium tools	use cases and test framework specification; maritime: performance of maritime testbed	maritime: analysis of network performance, reporting of results	text; maritime: Nemo and Qosium output files	Thousands of records	both	no	deliverables (5G-Routes Project Repository) ; for maritime: VTT repository	Project duration	deliverables: public; maritime: maritime solution partners
TELIA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
UNITI	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VEDIA	Vedia	Consortium	Use case planning	project planning	N/A	text/figures	N/A	Both	N/A	cloud/Vedia	N/A	Consortium partners
WINGS	All UC participants	Project partners	Use Case 5.2 requirements	To identify all the requirements and KPIs that have to be met for use case 5.2	Data Analysis	Text	Specific KPI values	Public		deliverables (5G-Routes Project Repository)	Project duration + longer as part of public deliverables	All project partners & external readers of deliverables

Table 7: WP2 Data Management Plan

Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
EEE	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ADS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ADSF	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
PV	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ATOS	ATOS	Enablers capabilities	Technical requirements	Integration	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Project duration	Enablers leaders
BRA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
CTTC	CTTC	Technological enablers traces, CTTC 5G testbed	sequence and architectural diagrams of TEs interaction, measured enabler performance operations and CTTC testbed working logs, enablers artifacts (container images), enabler source code (.py), API description	project needs for validating the design of TEs, interactions among them (interoperability tests) and its interaction with a MANO platform, generate troubleshooting/configuration documents to operate the CAM Services Platform	Filtering for process/debug/integration purposes	log files (.txt), documents (.docx), presentations (.pptx), images (.png, .jpg)	N/A	confidential	No	CTTC, 5G-Routes Project Repository, 5G-Routes Gitlab repository	Project duration	Technical Enablers Owners (feedback when operations, deployments done)

EBOS	EBOS	CAM use cases & Lab/field trials	Technical specifications UML diagrams KPI calculations and representation	As part of the implementation of the tenant web portal	Storing, filtering and presentation	.XML .XLS	Some thousands of records	Public	No	Tenant portal deployed as a cloud-native application/database at CTC testbed to facilitate end-to-end testing of integrated CAM service platform	Project duration	CAM use cases and rest of the partners will have view access
EVR	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ENIDE	ENIDE	UC definitions	Tech specifications coming from UC definitions	Implementation and integrations of the tenant web portal and enablers	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD		TBD	TBD	TBD
CERTH	N/A	Open Datasets	Mobility Traces and Spatial Data for Open Street Maps	Implementation and integrations of the enablers developed by CERTH	Cleaned and transformed to be used as input to AI algorithms	.csv	Some Hundreds of thousands of records (approx. 10 GB)	Public	No	CERTH Premises	Project duration	CERTH
ILS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VED	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
IQU	IQU	CTTC testbed, innovation of technological enablers	KPIs, Requirements	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	N/A	IQU	N/A	Consortium partners

LMT	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
SWA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	.doc, .xls, .csv ETSI standar ds for C-ITS (in output) , proprie tary format s (in input)	N/A	Both	No (data only collected for testing purposes)	Swarco Cloud	Raw data - 1-week Aggregated KPIs - Project duration	Partners and Public authorities (Valka/Valga) will only be able to access to the services
TTU	TTU	Simulated data for V2X positioning task 2.3 based on 5G 3GPP release 16 and beyond	Test vectors of positioning reference signal (PRS signals) from 5G	Project needs to develop algorithms for positioning	processing to calculate vehicle coordinate s and performan ce evaluation of the algorithms	CSV, matfile s, png	PRS signal itself is several bytes but for the algorith ms we need large data set for training	both		TTU	Project duration	CTTC for positioning service placement, and other partners who will need the data
VTT	VTT	data collected during position measurement campaigns	High and low precision location data, 5G network radio performance and QoS data	development of enablers and improvement of position accuracy	algorithm developme nt	JSON, CSV	depends on the configura tions, software /hardwar e compone nts, and	Both	No (data only collected for testing purposes)	VTT	project duration	VTT and use case participants

							number of trials					
TELIA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
UNITI	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VEDIA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
WINGS	Data is not stored, hence no owner.	Collecting data from OBU, RSU, smartphones and various sensors for the AI/ML developed in T2.2 and UC5.2	User/vehicle location, vehicle attributes (speed, revs, temperature), camera feed & pics	Location is needed to identify users about to change networks (roaming) and to initiate resource pre-allocation at the visiting network. Sensor data is needed as input to the AI/ML algorithm to perform slice negotiation and risk assessment	data fusion & analytics processing, license plate recognition from camera pictures	All data are transmitted in text/CSV format.	depends on number of users per trial. Data is transmitted in a timescale below 1 sec.	confidential		WINGS Cloud/Edge server * (Data is only stored for post-processing and KPI calculations. Once the necessary metrics are calculated detailed data are deleted. No permanent storage of data.	2-4 weeks	WINGS. Data encryption during transmission and anonymization techniques will be applied

Table 8: WP3 Data Management Plan

Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
EEE	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ADS	ADS and use case owner	Use cases analysis	Satellite connectivity concepts	project needs	N/A	mainly .doc	tbd	both	No	5G-Routes Project Repository	project duration	Consortium partners
ADSF	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
PV	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ATOS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
BRA	BRA, ATOS	Use cases analysis, 5g architecture analysis	Documentation, deliverable contribution	Anali needs and WP1 objectives	N/A	.doc	N/A	Public	No	5G-Routes Project Repository	Project duration	Consortium partners
CTTC	CTTC	CTTC 5G testbed, CTTC personnel	CTTC testbed deployment logs and operation logs sequence diagrams (interaction enablers-use case), infrastructure diagrams and descriptions	As part of the lab trial validations for use cases and its interactions with enablers, generate troubleshooting/ configuration documents and logs to operate the CAM Services Platform in field trial	Filtering for process debug/validation purposes of Use cases (e.g., UC1.1, UC1.3, UC4.1, UC4.2, Roadwarning UC)	log files (.txt), documents (.docx), diagrams (.png, .vsdx, .xml)	N/A	confidential to the consortium (use of use case owner)	No	CTTC, 5G-Routes Project Gitlab Repository , 5G-Routes Teams	Project duration	Use case owners to validate its development, project consortium for infrastructure diagrams and descriptions

EBOS	EBOS	Lab trials data	row data	As part of the execution of the tenant web portal	Storing, filtering and presentation	.XML .XLS	Some thousands of records	Public	No	Tenant portal deployed as a cloud-native application /database at CTTC testbed to facilitate end-to-end testing of integrated CAM service platform	Project duration	CAM use cases Leaders
EDI	EDI	Lab and field tests, various recordings from test vehicle sensors	Point clouds, HD maps, vehicle kinematics data	Use-case analysis and validation, data visualization	Generation of (HD) maps, various calculations for UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.2, T3.2	.pcd, rosbag, candump, HD map formats	N/A	Both	No	EDI cloud / SharePoint	At least project duration	Consortium partners
EVR	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ENIDE	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
CERTH	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ILS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VED	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
IQU	IQU	CTTC testbed	KPIs	project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	IQU	N/A	Consortium partners
LMT	LMT, TELIA	5G SA Core and UCs vehicle data - racetrack Bikernieki, cross border	5G network infrastructure data (MEC, Orchestration, metrics, KPIs,	project needs	5G network deployment at cross border Valka-	various	TBC during project execution	Both	no	LMT cloud and 5G-Routes Project Repository	project duration	Consortium partners

		trials Valga-Valga	etc.), vehicle data & KPIs		Valga and CAM UCs: UC1.1., UC1.2, UC1.3, UC2.1, UC3.1, UC3.2,.							
SWA	City of Valga/ SWA	Data acquired from devices installed in specific locations to develop the trials	Traffic Light Data, Sensors Data, KPI's	Base for C-ITS services	Elaboration of C-ITS messages	ETSI standards for C-ITS (in output) , proprietary formats (in input)	Real time data per two intersections	Confidential	No	SWA Cloud	Raw data - 1 week, Aggregated KPIs - Project duration	Partners will only be able to access the services
TTU	TTU	TTU 5G-IoT testbed and TTU 5G D2D SideLink testbed	Data from OBD dongles/sensors (monitor vehicles' condition).	Usecase 3.2 and other project needs (usecases)	Developing machine learning algorithms for UC3.2	REST, JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) and MQTT.	Thousands of records	Both		TTU	Project duration	UC leaders and participants
VTT	VTT	use case tests with prototype vehicles, tests on the integration of the use cases with the CAM services platform	vehicle data, communication data metrics	use case validation, service integration	use case verification , KPI analysis, performance analysis	format described in D2.7, Qosium format	tbd	both	no (data collected with prototype vehicles during controlled tests)	VTT	project duration	Consortium partners

TELIA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
UNITI	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VEDIA	Vedia	VCU (Vedia IoT gateway)	GNSS positioning including RTK (Real time kinematics) assistant data, temperature	supply chain connectivity	Vedia CaaS collects sample data	NMEA184	test IoT devices + simulation	confidential	No	Vedia, test participants	project life time	Vedia, VTT, Taltech, Enide, Cumucore
WINGS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table 9: WP4 Data Management Plan

Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
EEE	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ADS	ADS and use case owner	Use cases analysis	Satellite connectivity KPIs	project needs	tbd	mainly .doc	tbd	both	No	5G-Routes Project Repository	project duration	Consortium partners
ADSF	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
PV	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ATOS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
BRA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
CTTC	CTTC	CTTC 5G testbed	CTTC testbed working and deployment logs/traces of enablers, use cases logs deployed through CAM Services Platform to validate UC developments and integration with enablers	project needs for complementing field trials (e.g., help to confirm field trials cloud deployments by comparing with lab trial cloud infrastructure deployment), generate troubleshooting/configuration and log documents to operate the CAM Services Platform	N/A	log files (.txt), diagrams (.png, .vsdx)	N/A	confidential to the consortium (infrastructure owners, use case owner purposes)	No	CTTC, 5G-Routes Teams Repository	Project duration	UCs owners request/collect validation data and experience measurements from the CTTC testbed (e.g., deployment time)

EBOS	EBOS	CAM use cases & field trials	row data	As part of the execution of the tenant web portal	Storing, filtering and presentation	.XML .XLS	Some thousands of records	Public	No	Tenant portal deployed as a cloud-native application /database at CTTC testbed to facilitate end-to-end testing of integrated CAM service platform	Project duration	CAM use cases leaders
EDI	EDI	vehicles	vehicle kinematics data, sensor data (lidar, radar, cameras, GNSS etc.)	KPI calculation	UC performance calculations	rosvbag, canudp, csv, pcap	N/A	Both	No	EDI cloud	At least project duration	CAM use-case participants
EVR	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ENIDE	ENIDE	UC 3.2 and 5.1	driving style characterization, predictive temperature alert	UC execution	Machine learning	JSON	TBD	TBD		TBD	TBD	ENIDE

CERTH	CERTH, VEDEC OM	UC3.3 Large-scale pilot - User evaluation tests. Mobile Roadwork device used in UC 3.3	User evaluation Questionnaire: System Usability Survey (SUS), User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ), Automation Trust Index (SATI), Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). (for Mobile Roadwork device) C-ITS transmitted and received message logs, KPIs	User acceptance and user experience assessment of UC3.3. (for Mobile Roadwork device) UC evaluation and KPI calculation	Excel, (for Mobile Roadwork device) calculation of KPIs	.doc, .xls (google forms output) . (for Mobile Roadwork device) csv	depending on no of users recruited . (for Mobile Roadwork device) depending on the number of trials	both	(for Mobile Roadwork device) No only metadata are stored	5G-Routes Project Repository , User profile in hard copies only at CERTH. (for Mobile Roadwork device) data are stored on the device and uploaded on Tennant Web	Project lifetime	Use of data: CERTH, Access: All Consortium partners
ILS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VED	VEDEC OM	Vehicles for UC 3.3	Vehicle data, C-ITS message logs, KPIs	KPI calculation and performance evaluation	calculation of KPIs	json (or csv)	TBD depending on the number of trials	Both	No only metadata are stored	VEDECOM vehicles and server Logs uploaded on Tenant Web	Project duration	Raw Data usage: VEDECOM Access to data on Tenant Web: All consortium partners
IQU	IQU	CTTC testbed	KPIs	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	No	CTTC,IQU	N/A	Consortium partners

LMT	LMT, TELIA, EEE	Large-scale cross-border field trials Valka-Valga	5G network infrastructure data (MEC, Orchestration, metrics, KPIs, etc.), CAM vehicle data & KPIs from UCs	To perform large scale cross-border trials by validating 5G functionalities over 3GPP R.16 and R.17.	TBC	various	TBC	Both	no	LMT and 5G- Routes Project Repository	Project lifetime	?
SWA	City of Valga/ SWA	UC 2.1 deployment of the lab trial and large-trial	Evaluation of performance of the CCAM systems based on 5G and AI (Traffic Light Data, Sensors Data)	Assessment of the continuity of the service base on 5G to provide enhanced CCAM functionalities and services for VRU's and autonomous "drivers"	Elaboration and analysis of the C-ITS messages	ETSI standards for C-ITS (in output), proprietary formats (in input)	Real time data per two intersections	Confidential	No	SWA Cloud	Raw data - 1 week, Aggregated KPIs - Project duration	Partners will only be able to access the services
TTU	TTU	TTU 5G-IoT testbed and TTU 5G D2D SideLink testbed	Data from OBD dongles/sensors (monitor vehicles' condition).	Usecase 3.2 and other project needs (usecases)	Developing machine learning algorithms for UC3.2	REST, JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) and MQTT.	Thousands of records	Both		TTU	Project duration	UC leaders and participants
VTT	VTT	use case trials measurements	use case trials measurements (logging at application level, Qosium results), processed use case trials measurements	KPI calculation, use case evaluation	calculation of KPIs, reporting of results	CSV files (format in D2.7), Qosium output files	Thousands of records	both	no (for vehicles: only controlled tests; for video in UC1.3: data is only streamed,	VTT, Tenant Web	duration of the project	Evaluation team

									and not stored)			
TELIA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
UNITI	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VEDIA	Vedia	VCU (Vedia IoT gateway)	GNSS positioning including RTK (Real time kinematics) assistant data, temperature	supply chain connectivity	Vedia CaaS collects sample data	NMEA184	test IoT devices + simulation	confidential	No	Vedia, test participants	project life time	Vedia, VTT, Taltech, Enide, Cumucore
WINGS	WINGS	5G testbeds, networks and components participating in the test and field trials for the WINGS led use case (UC5.2)	Network and application level measurement s/KPIs such as throughput, latency, reliability, etc.	Performance evaluation of the network and developed applications	Data analytics & post processing	textual /CSV format	unknown (depending on number and duration of tests/field trials)	Public		Network & testbed providers, WINGS application server.	for the duration of the project.	All partners

Table 10: WP5 Data Management Plan

Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
EEE	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ADS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ADSF	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
PV	PV	Sensors	Images and 3D point cloud	To perform railway infrastructure monitoring	Data collection, post processing, long term storage and visualisation	Video and image files, data tables	N/A	Confidential		Edge and PV data centre	N/A	Partners will be able to access data via visualisation service
ATOS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
BRA	BRA	Brainstorm market and commercialization strategy analysis	Documentation, deliverable contribution	Analysis of market strategy	N/A	.doc	N/A	Public	No	5G-Routes Project Repository	SharePoint project file repository	Consortium partners
CTTC	CTTC	CTTC 5G testbed, innovation of technological enablers, IPRs / patent filing	scientific publications, patent document	project needs	N/A	Documents (.docx, .pdf)	N/A	Confidential	No	CTTC	Project Duration	Consortium Partners sharing the activity
EBOS	EBOS	IPRs and Patent related documents (innovation/patenting questionnaires) Data management	Doc, Excel	input to D5.1/D5.2/D5.5 but also for patent selection and filing	Data collection, long term storage	.doc, .xls	<100 files	Confidential	no	5G-Routes Project Repository	Project Duration	Innovation and Commercialisation Board

		plan related docs										
EVR	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ENIDE	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
CERTH	CERTH	MAMCA Forms, Interviews, Focus Groups	Doc, Excel	MAMCA Analysis, CBA input	AHP, Excel (statistical analysis)	Excel	n=no of stakeholders providing feedback	Confidential		CERTH	Project Duration	WP5 Partners
ILS	ILS	Commercialisation/ innovation/ patenting questionnaires, working groups	Doc, Excel	input to D5.1/D5.2/ patent selection and filing	N/A	Excel	6	Confidential	no	ILS	Project Duration	I&CB
VED	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
IQU	IQU	IQU's testbed, innovation of technological enablers	KPIs, scientific publications	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	N/A	IQU	N/A	Consortium or public
LMT	LMT	Development of business models and commercialization analysis based on outcomes from 5G network deployment at Valka-Valga, UCs, cross-border trials, race track "Bikernieki".	Various.	Both: a) for projects needs and Deliverables; b) for analysing 5G network and CAM solutions for deployment & commercial	Quantitative and qualitative analysis of information	Majority - .doc, .xls, but could be other in other formats.	TBC	Both	Both. Consent will be asked during data collection	LMT	Depends on type of data: some data during project duration, other part - permanent	Depends on type of data.

				lisation needs.								
SWA	City of Valga/ SWA	Development of business models and commercialization analysis according to UC 2.1 outcomes	Publications, reports	Inputs to WP5 Deliverables	Quantitative and qualitative analysis of information	.doc, .xls	According to the information acquired	both	No	SWA cloud	Raw data - 1 week, Aggregated KPIs - Project duration	Consortium Partners
TTU	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VTT	VTT	data collected during exploitation activities	TBC	input to deliverables	Quantitative and qualitative analysis of information	text	TBC	both	no	TBC	to be agreed with consortium	dependent on data
TELIA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
UNITI	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VEDIA	Vedia	data collected during exploitation activities + patent application	N/A	data collected during exploitation activities	Quantitative and qualitative analysis of information	text	N/A	both	N/A	N/A	N/A	Inlecom + consortium or public (depends on data type)

WINGS	WINGS	Test and field trial results, cost items, bibliography, user acceptance questionnaire.	Cost of equipment purchased, cost of development & deployment, cost of maintenance and support, bibliographic data on market penetration, metrics from tests/trials regarding performance improvement and developed solution results. Questionnaire responses.	Perform an impact assessment for the WINGS developed solution, as well as a market and business plan for further exploitation, market impact, innovation potentials, etc.	Data analytics and post-processing	various	unknown	Confidential		WINGS and other partners facilities	permanent	WINGS
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Table 11: WP6 Data Management Plan

Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
EEE	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ADS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ADSF	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
PV	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ATOS	ATOS	Contributions to 5GPPP WGs	collaboration actions 5GPPP	keep track and coordinate activities around 5gppp	N/A	shared excel file	N/A	confidential to consortium	N/A	N/A	project duration	whole consortium
BRA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
CTTC	CTTC	CTTC contribution to dissemination activities, research activities	dissemination related, meeting participants, scientific publications, presentations, participation in relevant venues (conferences, expositions, PhD Schools, tutorials, etc.), text for posts in social networks	project needs	N/A	documents (.docx), slides (.pptx), social network posts (text + images), latex files	N/A	Public	N/A	deliverables (web); scientific papers (zenodo); videos and promos (Social Networks); brochures/rollups (5G-Routes Project Repository); scientific publications pre-prints (CTTC)	project duration	Consortium or public
EBOS	EBOS	EBOS contribution to dissemination	articles, social media posts	project dissemination activities	published on social media	emails, photos	<50	both	no	5G-Routes Project Repository	Project duration	Consortium or public

EDI	EDI	EDI contribution to dissemination activities	articles, social media posts, presentations at events	Project dissemination activities	N/A	text files, presentation files, audio-visual media	N/A	both	No	5G-ROUTES project repository	project duration	Consortium and public
EVR	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ENIDE	ENIDE	ENIDE contribution to dissemination	social media posts, presentations	Dissemination activities	N/A	N/A	N/A	both	No	N/A	N/A	ENIDE for editing, consortium and public for viewing
CERTH	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ILS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VED	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
IQU	IQU	IQU contribution to dissemination activities	dissemination related, meeting participants, etc.	Project needs	N/A	N/A	N/A	Both	N/A	IQU	N/A	Consortium or public
LMT	LMT	LMT contribution to dissemination activities	Presentations, participants' lists of the meetings, events etc, articles, social media posts.	For project dissemination activities	N/A	Different formats	N/A	both	No	LMT	Project duration	Consortium or public
SWA	SWA	Contribution to dissemination and papers elaboration	meetings, events etc, articles, social media posts.	Project dissemination activities	N/A	N/A	N/A	both	No	SWA	Project duration	Consortium or public
TTU	TTU	TTU's contribution to dissemination activities (e.g. scientific publications, white papers, tutorials and PhD schools)	Presentations, papers, lectures notes, list of participants, etc.	Dissemination and evaluation of dissemination activities	tbc	MS PowerPoint, Word, etc.	tbd	both		5G-Routes Project Repository	Project duration	Consortium partners

VTT	VTT	contributions to dissemination and exploitation	dissemination related	dissemination	n/a	dissemination formats	n/a	diss: public; expl: both		5G-Routes Project Repository	Project duration	diss: public
TELIA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
UNITI	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VEDIA	Vedia	Vedia/Consortium	test data/text/figures	piloting/testing/dissemination	N/A	text/figures	N/A	both	N/A	cloud/Vedia	N/A	5G ROUTES participants
WINGS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table 12: WP7 Data Management Plan

Lead Partner (Data Processor)	Owner of the data	Data Origin	Data Type	Purpose of collecting	Data Processing Activities	Data Format	Quantity	Public / Confidential to the consortium	Personal Data (Yes/No)	Data Storage Location	Data Storage Duration	Which partner will use the data / has access to it?
EEE	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ADS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ADSF	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
PV	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ATOS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
BRA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
CTTC	CTTC	Internal financial statements from project management office	Task effort and financial expenditure figures	Project management needs	Storage	.xls	1 every quarter	Confidential	No	CTTC	Project duration	CTTC, Project Coordination
EBOS	EBOS	Official deliverables	Quality review information	Quality review	N/A	.doc .xls	N/A	both	yes	5G-Routes Project Repository	Project duration	Consortium
EVR	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ENIDE	ENIDE	Official deliverables	Quality review information	Quality review process	N/A	Documents	N/A	Confidential		N/A	Project lifetime	Consortium
CERTH	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ILS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VED	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
IQU	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
LMT	LMT	Employment contracts etc.	Personal data of LMT employees, etc.	For management needs	Safe storage	Documents	N/A	Confidential	yes	LMT	Project lifetime	LMT and EC
SWA	SWA	WP7 work and internal financial statements	N/A	For management needs	N/A	documents	N/A	Confidential	No	SWA	Project duration and beyond	SWA, consortium and EC

TTU	TTU	Work contracts etc.	Personal data of employees and PhD students	Project management needs	Storage	Text	tbc	Confidential		TTU	Project duration and beyond	TTU (and European Commission)
VTT	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
TELIA	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
UNITI	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
VEDIA	Vedia	Vedia/Consortium	HR data/text/figures	reporting/dissemination	N/A	text/figures	N/A	Confidential	N/A	Ericsson/Vedia	N/A	Ericsson
WINGS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

4.3.1 Data Overview

A detailed analysis of the data collected by project partners, as documented in the DMP Registry, reveals the following key aspects:

- **Primary Storage:**
- SharePoint served as the primary repository for storing documents and confidential data specific to the consortium. This included dissemination materials, deliverables, market analysis information, contact lists, and other project-related documentation. Access was restricted to consortium members to ensure security and compliance.
- **Data Collected During Trial Execution:**
 - Trial data was initially stored in the SharePoint repository and subsequently transferred to a secure database hosted on the Tenant Web Portal hosted in CTTC environment.
 - The data comprised both public (e.g., 5G network data) and confidential (e.g., traffic light or sensor data) datasets.
 - No personal data was included in the trial datasets.
 - The collected data required no special treatment, such as anonymization, as no personal information was involved.
 - As agreed by the consortium partners, by the end of the project, final datasets, public deliverables, and other public data were prepared for sharing through open-access repositories such as Zenodo and Open Research Europe.
- **Personal Data:**
- Personal data gathered during webinars, events, exploitation activities, and employment-related documents (e.g., contracts) were securely stored in SharePoint with restricted access limited to consortium members. All personal data handling complied with GDPR and ethical guidelines, with explicit consent obtained during data collection.
- **Project Deliverables:**
- All project deliverables were securely stored in SharePoint. Public deliverables were additionally shared via Zenodo and Open Research Europe and published on the project's website to enhance accessibility and visibility.
- **Data Retention:**
- Data collected during the project was securely stored for the project's lifetime. If necessary, data may be retained for up to five years post-project to facilitate final closing activities, after which it will be permanently deleted. Partners requiring access to specific data during the project duration could submit a request to the Project Coordinator.
- **Ongoing Evaluation and Updates:**
- The DMP Registry was continuously evaluated throughout the project lifecycle, based on input from consortium partners. Updates and enhancements were implemented as necessary to reflect changes in data collection, storage, and sharing processes, ensuring alignment with the project's evolving needs and requirements.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable presents the final version of the 5G-ROUTES Data Management Plan (DMP), outlining the comprehensive framework established for managing data throughout the project lifecycle. It encapsulates the foundational rules and guidelines that governed the creation, processing, utilization, and exploitation of data during the project. The DMP ensured compliance with ethical standards and adherence to GDPR regulations, safeguarding personal data while supporting the project's research and innovation objectives.

The structured data management approach implemented in the 5G-ROUTES project adhered to the FAIR principles as defined by the European Commission. It incorporated robust policies and procedures to manage both public and confidential data responsibly, ensuring their long-term usability and accessibility where applicable.

By the conclusion of the project in M54, all data collection activities across WPs and partners were successfully completed, documented, and stored in a secure, organised manner. Section 4.3 of this deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of all data collected, as recorded in the finalized DMP Registry. This Registry was a critical tool throughout the project, enabling continuous tracking, refinement, and organization of data. This living document ensured that all datasets were appropriately categorized, and accessible to the relevant consortium partners.

Each WP Leader played a pivotal role in maintaining the accuracy of the DMP Registry by defining and describing datasets specific to their WPs. Updates to the Registry were performed every three months, or more frequently, when necessary, with eBOS monitoring data management activities as part of WP5. This proactive approach ensured that all data management processes remained aligned with the evolving needs of the project.

To uphold ethical standards, the DMP mandated the use of specific templates for trials involving participants from outside the consortium. These templates, established in deliverable D7.7 and forming part of the Ethics Protocol, included:

- **Informed Consent Form Example Template**
- **Anonymous Informed Consent Template**
- **Non-Anonymous Informed Consent Template**

Additionally, the "Non-Disclosure Agreement for External Advisory Board Members" template, defined in deliverable D8.1 H – Requirement No. 1 (Dissemination Level: CO), was an integral part of the DMP. The use of these templates ensured synchronization between the DMP and the project's Ethics Protocol, guaranteeing that all data collection activities adhered to ethical requirements and respected the rights and privacy of participants. As part of the project's commitment to open science, public datasets and deliverables were shared through open-access repositories such as Zenodo and Open Research Europe, maximizing the visibility and impact of project results. Confidential data, in contrast, remained securely stored and was handled in compliance with the project's data protection and intellectual property guidelines.

The 5G-ROUTES DMP has demonstrated a robust and efficient framework for managing data in large-scale, multi-partner research initiatives. It has not only facilitated the ethical and responsible handling of project data but has also laid a strong foundation for the reuse and dissemination of research outputs. This final DMP underscores the project's dedication to maximizing the impact of its findings while adhering to the highest standards of data governance and scientific integrity.

6 References

- [1] Open Research Data Pilot (ORD Pilot) <https://www.openaire.eu/what-is-the-open-research-data-pilot>
- [2] Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/>
- [3] Open Research Europe <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>
- [4] European OpenAIRE <https://www.openaire.eu/>
- [5] General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), 27 April 2016, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>
- [6] Open Access guidelines for H2020 projects, https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm
- [7] Open Access Publishing, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/computer-science/open-access-publishing>
- [8] How subscription based scholarly journals can convert to open access: A review of approaches, 19 September 2016, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/leap.1056>
- [9] Zenodo General Policies, <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/#:~:text=Retention%20period%3A%20Items%20will%20be,next%200%20years%20at%20least>
- [10] Zenodo DOI versioning, <https://zenodo.org/record/1256592/files/zenodo-doi-versioning.pdf?download=1>
- [11] Digital Object Identifier (DOI) handbook, https://www.doi.org/doi_handbook/2_Numbering.html
- [12] International Standard Audio-Visual Number (ISAN), <https://www.isan.org/>
- [13] International Standard Book Number (ISBN), <https://www.isbn-international.org/content/what-isbn#:~:text=An%20ISBN%20is%20an%20International,digit%20to%20validate%20the%20number.>
- [14] International Standard Recording Code (ISRC), <https://isrc.ifpi.org/en/>
- [15] International Standard Serial Number (ISSN), <https://www.issn.org/>
- [16] International Standard Text Code (ISTC), <http://www.istc-international.org/>
- [17] Digital Object Identifier (DOIs) for Research Data, <https://support.datacite.org/docs/doi-basics>
- [18] DublinCore (Dublin Core Metadata Element Set), <https://dublincore.org/>
- [19] MARCXML (MARC 21 XML Schema), <https://www.loc.gov/standards/marcxml/>
- [20] BibTeX, <http://www.bibtex.org/>
- [21] Citation Style Language (CSL), <https://citationstyles.org/>
- [22] DataCite Metadata Schema, <https://schema.datacite.org/>
- [23] Mendeley Exporting Papers Guides, <https://www.mendeley.com/guides/using-citation-editor/10-exporting-papers>
- [24] Creative Commons licenses (CC) BY-SA https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Open_Content_-_A_Practical_Guide_to_Using_Creative_Commons_Licences/The_Creative_Commons_licencing_scheme

Annex 1: DPO Appointment Template

TO: 5G-ROUTES Project Consortium

SUBJECT: Declaration of Compliance with GDPR for the project 5G-ROUTES and DPO Appointment

With this letter, **PARTNER NAME** is declaring their compliance with the GDPR as in force since 01 September 2020 and relating to collection and/or processing of personal data of EU citizens. **PARTNER NAME** is aligned with the GDPR in an approach to ensure that effective measures are in place to protect the personal data of EU members, customers, employees and other stakeholders and ensure their lawful, fair and transparent processing.

As relates to the personal data involved in the 5G-ROUTES [H2020, GA No: 951867] project, PARTNER NAME confirms that:

- An internal policy is in place relating to personal data protection, developed by **PARTNER NAME's** senior management and communicated to all employees through a comprehensive awareness training programme.
- This internal policy is being used as a lawful basis under the GDPR for any data processed.
- All internal staff understand their roles in the processing and protection of personal data, including confidentiality requirements.
- All personal data under processing have been identified, including special categories whenever involved.
- For the cases where processing is based on required consent, **PARTNER NAME** has provisioned the suitable steps to ensure clear, free consent given/recorded in a clear language explaining all the terms and conditions for the personal data processing (including purpose, right to be forgotten, duration, access by third parties, rectification, EC FAIR treatment etc.).
- Planning for data protection is fully foreseen in new or changed services and systems, including keeping use of personal data to the intended purpose as well as protecting it.

PARTNER NAME has the following dedicated DPO, as senior member appointed and with a role fully aligned with Art.39 of GDPR in informing, advising and monitoring data processing compliance.

- Name: xxxxxxxxx
- ID/Date of Birth: xxxxxxxxx
- E-mail: xxxxxxxxx
- Phone Number: xxxxxxxxx

PARTNER NAME commits to continuously developing and improving their data protection policies and controls, guided by legal requirements and updated regulations and the needs and preferences of our partners, members and customers.

Yours sincerely,

Name: xxxxxxxxx
Title: xxxxxxxxx
Date: xxxxxxxxx

SIGNATURE

.....

Annex 2: DPO Per Partner

Organisation	DPO Name	DPO Email
ERICSSON EESTI AS	Ulle Tiitmaa	ulle.tilmaa@ericsson.com
AIRBUS DEFENCE AND SPACE GMBH	Hartwig Oliver Boesl	oliver.boesl@airbus.com
AIRBUS DEFENCE AND SPACE SAS	Hartwig Oliver Boesl	oliver.boesl@airbus.com
PASAZIERU VILCIENS	Jana Klintaja	jana.klintaja@ldz.lv
ATOS SPAIN SA	Fatima Aparicio Prieto Ricardo Esteban Lopez Crespo	dles-proteccion.datos@atos.net
BRAINSTORM MULTIMEDIA S.L.	Miguel Churruca Soto	mchurruca@brainstorm3d.com
CENTRE TECNOLOGIC DE TELECOMUNICACIONS DE CATALUNYA	Nadina Del Moral Roura	nadina.moral@cttc.cat
EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LTD	Sozos Karageorgiou Christos Skoufis	sozosk@ebos.com.cy christoss@ebos.com.cy
EESTI RAUDTEE AS	Helen Hindrichson-Nairis	helen.hindrichson-nairis@evr.ee
ENIDE SOLUTIONS.S.L	David Quesada	david.quesada@enide.com
ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TEKNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	Ioannis Chalinidis	dpo@certh.gr
INLECOM INNOVATION ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	Ioanna Fevgadiotou	ioanna.fevgadiotou@inlecomsystems.com
INSTITUT VEDECOM	Duclos Sarah	sarah.duclos@vedecom.fr
IQUADRAT INFORMATICA SL	Melani Gurdiel	pm@iquadrat.com
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Annex 3: Data Protection Policy

Introduction

The GDPR is the EU Regulation that governs the privacy and security of personal data and it is applied by all members states. Alongside the GDPR national laws add to the specifications of data privacy and protection at each member state. Ever since its enforcement in 2018, the GDPR has forced organizations to think twice on the reasons they collect and process data restricting collection and processing to the minimum amount necessary. Additionally, the GDPR assigns nine rights to the data subjects which they can exercise at any point, granting them control of processing of their own data. For the purposes of this Policy the GDPR definitions, as set in Article 4, apply. In addition, the following are applied:

- **“Personal data”** means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person that is processed by any Project Partner and Policy Recipient during execution of the Project.
- **“Controller”** means the owner of the data (usually the creator of the data itself), unless otherwise expressly clarified in this Policy or elsewhere in Project deliverables and/or reports.
- **“Processor”** means each Project Partner, unless otherwise expressly clarified in this Policy or elsewhere in Project deliverables and/or reports.
- **“Consent”** of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous and **in writing** indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her.
- **“Supervisory authority”** means the competent Data Protection Authorities within the Project Partners’ jurisdictions.

Definitions

Article 4 of the GDPR defines the terms used within the Regulation. Relevant definitions to this project are listed below:

- **personal data** as “any information relating to natural persons, that is or can be identified, even indirectly, by reference to any other information including a personal identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person
- **Special categories of data:** Special categories of personal data include data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation as well as the processing of genetic data and biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying an individual. In the event of such processing the Controller and/or Processor respectively comply with specific rules related to the processing of such data of special categories, as collecting specific informed consent from data subject and applying stricter safeguards. When the Controller and/or Processor relies on data subject's consent as a legal ground for processing special categories of data, it will meet all legal consent requirements; otherwise, they are only processed if and to the extent it is based on one of the legal grounds listed in the GDPR for the processing of such data.
- **Data processing** means any operation, or set of operations, carried out with or without the help of electronic or automated means, concerning the collection, recording, organization, keeping, interrogation, elaboration, modification, selection, retrieval, comparison, utilization, interconnection, blocking, communication, dissemination, erasure and destruction of data whether the latter are contained or not in data bank.
- **Data anonymisation:** Whenever possible, including non-detrimental to Project execution purposes, Controller and Project Partners shall undertake efforts to keep personal data processed by them for Project purposes anonymous or pseudonymous. According to the GDPR, “*anonymous information*” is information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person, or personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. In this context, the GDPR does not apply to the processing of such anonymous information, including for

statistical or research purposes. Similarly, “*pseudonymisation*” means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.

- **Controller:** By determining the purposes and means of the processing of personal data, unless otherwise expressly specified in this Policy, the Controller is considered by law as the “Controller” and it is the primary target of the provisions of the law.
- **Joint controller:** In the event that at any time during Project execution the Controller processes personal data in conjunction with a third party, by jointly determining the purposes and means of the processing, they both act as joint controller. Both joint controllers determine the mutual responsibilities with a specific arrangement.
- **Processor:** Unless otherwise specified expressly in this Policy, all Project Partners act as Processors during Project execution. A processor processes personal data on behalf of the Controller – that is, the Controller delegates all or part of the processing activities to them. In such event the Project contract assumes the role of the relevant required written agreement as per GDPR requirements. The processor warrants that it shall provide sufficient guarantees to ensure compliance with the GDPR, has implemented appropriate controls to meet data protection requirements defined by the agreement, instructions and/or legal requirements and ensures the protection of the rights of data subjects.
- **Data Protection Officer (DPO):** Whenever required, following applicable GDPR and Member State respective legal requirements, the Controller and each Processor, may designate a data protection officer (“DPO”) for assistance in monitoring internal compliance with GDPR.

Lawfulness of Processing

The GDPR restricts processing of personal data if it cannot be justified by one of the legal bases listed in Article 6 on the lawfulness of processing. Therefore, processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies:

- a) The data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes.
- b) Processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering a contract.
- c) Processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject.
- d) Processing is necessary to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person.
- e) Processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller.
- f) Processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests³ pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, where the data subject is a child.

Notice and Consent

Notice: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, provides the information required by law to the data subject in a concise, transparent, intelligible, and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, for any information addressed specifically to a child. The data protection notice informs data subjects about the processing of personal data relating to them, even when the personal data are not collected from them as well as of their rights, to let them verify the accuracy of the data and the lawfulness of the processing.

³ If “legitimate interest” is used as a basis, the interests that have preceded to the decision, need to be documented as well as any possible mitigating measures which will be taken to be able to proceed with personal data processing based on the defined interests.

Free and informed consent: Personal data are processed if and to the extent that the data subject has given valid consent to the processing for one or more specific purposes, or another legal basis for processing exists. Systems or applications can document the explicit consent of the data subject so that it can be evidenced at any time.

The data subject has the right to withdraw their consent at any time without affecting the lawfulness of data processing based on consent before its withdrawal.

Rights of Data Subjects

The GDPR requires that each Controller and/or Processor as appropriate, must facilitate the exercise of the data subject's rights, act on the request within a specific time frame and must communicate the information requested in an intelligible and easy to access form.

Right of access: Any individual must be able to exercise the right of access to data relating to him which are being processed.

Right to rectification: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request rectification of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases rectification is legitimate. If a data subject's request for rectification is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

Right to erasure: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request erasure of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases erasure is legitimate. If a data subject's request for erasure is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

Right to restriction of processing: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request restriction of processing of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases restriction is legitimate. If a data subject's request for restriction of processing is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

Right to data portability: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, determines which processes are subject to the right of data portability as well as when the requirements for such right are met. Data subject can request the organization to receive a machine-readable copy of the personal data the organization holds about them and where possible, enable the transfer of this data to another data controller.

Portability right can be exercised when:

- a) Processing operations are based on data subject's consent or on contract.
- b) Personal data concerns the data subject and are the same that the latter has provided to the organization.
- c) The right does not adversely affect rights and freedoms of others.
- d) The processing is carried out by automated means.

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, implements appropriate measures and procedures to provide data subject, who is entitled to, with a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable copy of the personal data it holds about him and where possible, to enable the transfer of this data to another data controller indicated by data subject.

Right to object: Where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, the data subjects have the right to object on grounds relating to their situation (unless the processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out for reasons of public interest). The right to object is explicitly brought to the attention of the data subject at the latest at the time of the first communication with the data subject, presented clearly and separately from any other information. Measures should be in place to assess such objections and to ensure that such processing ceases when the request is legitimate and needs to be respected. Data subjects have right to object, on request and free of charge, to the processing of personal data relating to them for purposes of direct marketing.

Automated decision making: Data subject has the right to object to any automatic decision-making (including profiling). Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, will have determined which processes entail automated decision-making (including profiling) and will have established measures to allow data subjects to object to such automated decision making and profiling. Suitable measures are in place to safeguard the data

subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interest, at least the right to obtain human intervention on the part of the Company/controller, to express his or her point of view and to contest the decision.

Timely response to exercise of rights: Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must confirm to data subjects without delay whether data relating to them are processed and communicate the data to them in an intelligible form. Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should implement internal procedures in order to be able to provide a timely response to the requests of data subject for the exercise of his rights. Measures have to be implemented in a way that effectively allows an individual to exercise his or her right to personal data, and that enables Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, to respond to such request appropriately within the required timeframes.

Notification to recipients: In case of a legitimate exercise of rights to rectification, erasure, or restriction of processing recipients of the personal data should be informed of the rectification, erasure of that data or of the restriction of processing. Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for communicating any rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing to the recipients to whom the personal data has been disclosed and for disclosing these recipients to the data subject, if so requested. Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, about their processing activities must set up a relevant record, maintained in writing (including in electronic form) and made available easily and swiftly to the supervisory authority on request, as per applicable legal requirements within their respective Member States. The record of processing activities shall contain all the information required by GDPR. Consequently, the Controller shall have an up-to-date overview of all personal data processing activities and shall maintain records within the Project, that meet the legal requirements posed by the GDPR. By so doing, the Controller will be able to demonstrate compliance to any Supervisory Authority or other state or EU authority concerned. For the avoidance of doubt, each Project Partner carries the same responsibility above within its own respective organisation.

Data protection assessment

Article 35 of the GDPR refers to the need for a Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA). This refers to the obligation of the controller to conduct an impact assessment and to document it before starting the intended data processing. The DPIA assesses the risks of data processing alongside the impact to the data subject and it is required in case of:

- a) Systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons which is based on automated processing, including profiling, and on which decisions are based that produce legal effects concerning the natural person or similarly significantly affect the natural person.
- b) Processing on a large scale of special categories of data referred to in Article 9(1), or of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10; or
- c) Systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale.

Technical and organizational measures

The Controller and each Project Partner, as appropriate, adopts appropriate technical and organisational measures about Project execution (the “**Measures**”), and reviews and updates them where necessary, to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is complying with GDPR. Each Project Partner shall notify relevant Measures to the Controller in writing. In the event of any queries or further requests by the Controller, each Project Partner undertakes to address them duly and in writing. If any Project Partner has notified the Measures to its competent Supervisory Authority, it shall inform the Controller thereof, and shall provide respective copies thereof.

Data breach

According to the GDPR, all organizations processing personal data must have appropriate and adequate measures to prevent any attempts of personal data breaches. In the event of a data breach, mechanisms must be in place to mitigate the risks and minimize the impact on the data subject. Additionally, in the event of a data

breach the responsible Controller or Processor must notify their local Supervisory Authority immediately and not later than 72 hours after they become aware of the breach. If the breach carries significant risk of serious adverse effects on the data subject(s) or serious adverse consequences for the protection of personal data, the data subject must also be informed without undue delay. A specific register where the breaches must be recorded together with other information specified by the law, must be maintained by the Controller, and shown to the Supervisory Authority upon request. This register is an important element of the data protection documentation system. Project Partners need to notify immediately and in writing the Controller of any personal data breach within their respective organisations that affects execution of the Project in any way, and to cooperate with the Controller while applying relevant GDPR legal requirements.

Data to Third Countries

No international transfers of personal data are expected to take place during the Project lifecycle. In case that a Project Partner wishes to carry out such personal data processing, it shall notify the Project Coordinator in writing and in advance. Moreover, no server utilized by the Project, or file repository is located outside the EU.

Project Website and Cloud File Repository

Project website and document server includes privacy and cookies policies and are available in the following URLs:

- Project website Privacy Policy: <https://www.5g-routes.eu/privacy-policy/>
- Project website Cookies Policy: <https://www.5g-routes.eu/cookies-policy/>

Project cloud file repository of the Project (SharePoint) also provides privacy policies and GDPR compliance in the following URLs:

- SharePoint Privacy Policy: <https://www.microsoft.com/en-gb/privacy/privacystatement>
- SharePoint GDPR Compliance : <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/compliance/regulatory/gdpr>